

ENHANCING COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE AND ENGLISH MASTERY THROUGH CRITICAL THINKING IN EFL

Azizbek Mukhamedov

Associate professor, PhD, JSPU

Sarvinoz Doniyorova

Graduate Student, JSPU

Abstract: Critical thinking is an essential cognitive skill that enables individuals to analyze, evaluate, and synthesize information. This article explores the vital role of critical thinking in the development of both English language mastery and communicative competence. It examines how critical thinking facilitates deeper comprehension of linguistic structures, nuances of meaning, and the social-cultural contexts that underpin language use. Additionally, the article analyzes ways critical thinking fosters the ability to express ideas with clarity, persuasiveness, and sensitivity to diverse audiences. It offers a working definition of critical thinking and examines its influence on the development of speaking skills.

Keywords: Critical thinking, English as a Foreign Language (EFL), speaking skills, classroom activities, language fluency, Ted Talks.

Critical thinking, rooted in the teachings of ancient Greece and popularized by philosophers like John Dewey, is crucial in education. A prominent American philosopher and educator Dewey's works highlighted the importance of critical thinking as the active, persistent, and careful consideration of beliefs or supposed forms of knowledge. This concept, dating back to Socrates, has been central to educational reforms that emphasize critical reasoning over rote memorization (Dewey, 1910, p. 6). The idea of critical thinking has its origins in ancient Greece, notably through the teachings of Socrates, as acknowledged by his student Plato. Socrates' method of questioning and dialogue laid the groundwork for critical reasoning. Plato recognized Socrates as the earliest proponent of critical thinking during the classical period (5th c. - 4th c. BC).

The progressive education movement adopted critical thinking as a core instructional goal, offering a dynamic alternative to traditional methods such as rote memorization. While Dewey popularized the term in the early 20th century, the essence of critical thinking has been present in intellectual traditions for centuries.

The term «critical thinking» originates from the Greek word “kritikos” meaning «critic,» which refers to the ability to assess, discern, and evaluate intellectually. Various authors agree that critical thinking involves a combination of knowledge, cognitive skills, and a particular mindset essential for effective reasoning.

According to Edward M. Glaser, critical thinking involves an ‘unbiased evaluation and reflection on information and arguments,’ which aligns with Dewey’s educational goals (Glaser, cited in Halpern, 1996, p. 45).

John Dewey views it as the capacity to actively and skillfully use various cognitive processes such as conceptualization, application, analysis, synthesis, and evaluation to come to reasoned conclusions.

Richard Paul (1990) defines critical thinking as “the disciplined intellectual process of evaluating situations or ideas and making appropriate decisions” which is crucial in language learning where nuanced understanding is required (Paul, cited in Roberts & Billings, 1999).

Linda Elder, co-founder of the Foundation for Critical Thinking, defines it as the capability to think independently, consider various perspectives, and make decisions based on evidence and logical reasoning.

Brookfield and Preskill (1991) argue for the need to challenge assumptions and engage in reflective dialogue to enhance critical thinking, a strategy that complements the communicative approach in language teaching (Brookfield, 1991).

Critical thinking is a vital educational principle rooted in the teachings of many philosophers. Defined as the disciplined intellectual process of evaluating situations and making appropriate decisions, critical thinking involves a blend of knowledge, cognitive skills, and a particular mindset essential for effective reasoning. Influential figures and scholars have further elucidated its importance, especially in language learning, where nuanced understanding and reflective dialogue are crucial.

In studying the impact of task-based interactions on critical thinking, it is crucial to understand the related concept of communicative competence. Introduced by Hymes in 1972 and further elaborated by Canale and Swain in 1980, and Bachman in 1990, communicative competence refers to the ability to use language effectively and appropriately to achieve communicative goals in specific contexts. This competence combines both theoretical knowledge of a language and the practical skills necessary to apply that knowledge in real-world communication scenarios.

Grasping the concept of communicative competence is essential for understanding the impact of task-based interactions on critical thinking. It encompasses not only the theoretical knowledge of a language but also the practical abilities to utilize that knowledge effectively in various communication settings. By engaging in task-based interactions, individuals can develop and enhance their communicative competence, which in turn fosters critical thinking skills. This dual development of communicative competence and critical thinking is particularly significant in language learning, where the ability to analyze, evaluate, and apply language in nuanced ways is crucial. Thus, integrating task-based learning approaches that promote communicative competence

can significantly enhance the development of critical thinking skills in educational contexts.

Critical thinking enriches language learning by encouraging students to analyze, evaluate, and synthesize information. It supports deeper comprehension of linguistic structures and cultural contexts, essential for effective communication. There are several elements that influence a student's capacity to communicate in English language classes. These include motivation, classroom atmosphere, as well as teaching and learning contexts (Brown, H. D. (2007). Educators who are proficient know how to push students to excel. A modern competent language teacher tailors their methods and approaches to suit a student's learning preferences. This approach encourages students to engage more actively in group activities. The ability to think and act critically is one of the factors that impacts a learner's communication skills. By fostering critical thinking, learners enhance their English communication abilities. Consequently, promoting critical thinking encourages independent learning. Language acquisition is a challenging process. Both teachers and learners are concerned with maximizing opportunities for language practice in the classroom.

Various educational methods are being used to enhance students' critical thinking abilities. These methods are applicable not only to learning foreign languages but are also integrated into diverse subjects. Within English language courses, students are motivated to link what they know to real-world applications. In accordance with the language learning principles, instructors involve students in interactive exercises such as communication-based activities, simulations, role-play, and challenges that require critical thinking (Cottrell, S. 2011). Given that the primary goal of language acquisition is for its practical use in communication, the adoption of an efficient instructional approach is crucial.

To master English language based on critical thinking the tasks should not be only challenging, but also visually appealing and enjoyable. It is believed that poorly designed materials can lead to boredom and disinterest. Therefore, English language educators incorporate activities such as puzzles, word games, and engaging pictures to add a dynamic element to the tasks. The tasks are to be structured to progress from simple to complex, both in terms of content and format, and catered to various competencies. With a focus on critical thinking, key constructs are emphasized such as inferring information from oral and written texts, comparing and contrasting ideas, identifying advantages and disadvantages of different issues, distinguishing between facts and opinions, writing short compositions expressing their viewpoint with supporting arguments, conducting surveys and analyzing collected data, examining various types of readings, using logical reasoning to solve hypothetical scenarios, exploring and discussing issues from multiple perspectives (social, political, economic), analyzing implications, evaluating events and people's perspectives,

assessing the validity and applicability of alternative solutions, and reflecting on the social impact and consequences of different issues on our community (Halvorsen, A. 2005). Various tasks necessitate discussions, wherein the students are expected to express their perspectives and present arguments to support their decisions.

There are various available methods that can assist students in enhancing their critical thinking skills while practicing speaking in English. Engaging in elicitation tasks such as watching short animated videos, newscasts, posters, documentaries, TED talks, YouTube videos, dramas, and educational clips on the internet or messaging platforms can offer authentic and current educational content to create interesting and relevant lessons for students.

The use of multimedia resources such as TED Talks enhances critical thinking by providing “real-world contexts and expert perspectives” (www.ted.com; Kinoshita, 2003). These semi-academic talks can cover a wide range of topics including education, business, science, medicine, technology, sports, health, art, culture, and more. By focusing on the grammar, vocabulary, pronunciation, presentation style, main ideas, supporting examples, and arguments presented in these talks, students are encouraged to participate in group discussions where they analyze the speaker’s performance, classroom interactions, peer evaluations, and self-critiques. Each student is required to deliver a presentation on a chosen topic, following the same process of critical evaluation.

Critical thinking plays a vital role in self-reflection, enabling individuals to lead meaningful lives by justifying and reflecting on their values and decisions. By engaging in the aforementioned tasks, students learn to evaluate new ideas, select the most suitable ones, and cultivate the ability to think critically and engage in reflective and independent thinking.

In a communicative classroom, all the participants are collaborative. Effective learning depends on effective teaching. Teaching includes passion, ability, skills, active teaching, and interaction (Moon, J. 2008). A professional teacher is aware of students’ needs. Teaching English is not merely to explain the lesson, explain vocabulary, read aloud, give homework and that is done. An effective teacher should give instructions on how to learn this vocabulary, how to write an essay, how to write a composition, and so on.

A well-prepared teacher uses different skills in pedagogy in student-centered classes where the language context should be meaningful. The teacher assists and monitors the students while working on course assignments where the language is spoken and understood. While thinking critically, students try to relate the known information with the unknown, draw schemes, and relate thoughts with meanings. It is the teacher’s task to show them how to do this, to resolve and draw conclusions.

Critical thinking is a vital skill that helps students develop creativity and expand their vocabulary, language knowledge, and cultural understanding. Critical thinking activities like analytical reading and discussions expose students to new words and their contexts. By articulating thoughts and responding to others, students naturally improve their vocabulary.

When a student uses critical thinking combined with speaking skills in a classroom, several activities can facilitate and demonstrate this integration effectively. There are multiple classroom activities that effectively blend critical thinking with speaking skills, demonstrating how these can be integrated seamlessly in an educational setting. Integrating critical thinking into English classes involves engaging and visually appealing tasks, such as debates, Socratic seminars, role-plays, peer teaching and reflective oral journals (Vasilopoulos, G. 2008).

During debates, students are divided into groups, each representing different viewpoints on a controversial topic, such as “Should social media be regulated?” Each group researches their position, prepares arguments and counterarguments, and engages in a structured debate. This activity requires students to critically analyze information, anticipate opposing views, and articulate their arguments convincingly.

In a Socratic seminar, the class discusses a philosophical question or a piece of literature, guided by open-ended questions posed by the teacher. Students are encouraged to think deeply about the topic, pose questions to each other, and build upon others’ ideas. This reciprocal communication helps students refine their thoughts and articulate them clearly, fostering a deeper understanding. “Seminars provide an opportunity for students to make meaning and to think deeply about issues and ideas, different than the usual lessons of merely mastering information. Socratic seminars give students an opportunity to slow down their thinking and to elaborate on it, to test their ideas - ones just formed and ones learned in school Socratic seminars require students to summarize, analyze, synthesize, evaluate, and compare and contrast-cognitive processes that develop more coherent and better-developed perspectives”.

In Socratic seminars, everyone sits in a circle. This helps everyone talk to and really listen to each other. Students get to use their critical thinking a lot in these talks. They learn to look at things from different sides. The teacher helps guide the discussion but lets students lead it. This means students learn to think and speak for themselves. To make the discussions interesting, they use topics that are easy to understand but also deep. This makes students want to ask tough questions and find their own answers (Parker, W. C., & Hess, D. E. 2001).

When it comes to working together to solve problems, like how to build a city that’s good for the environment, students need to work as a team. They need to think about money, keeping the planet healthy, and what people need. They have to talk about their ideas clearly, make decisions together, and show how they can solve

problems. Before they start, they need to understand the problem really well. They ask questions like:

- *What's going on right now?*
- *Why did this problem start?*
- *Am I making any guesses without enough proof?*
- *What are some ways we might fix this problem, just from looking quickly?*

Role-plays can help students understand historical events, scientific concepts, or literature by acting out scenarios. For example, students could reenact a historical peace treaty negotiation. Students must research their roles, think critically about their character's perspective, and articulate their viewpoints within the context of the role-play. Role-playing and scenario discussions have a profound and long-term impact on students' personal and professional lives, extending far beyond the confines of the classroom. The benefits acquired and behaviors shaped during these activities are long-lasting.

Regular engagement in role-playing and scenario discussions equips students with the ability to navigate social situations with finesse. These activities help them develop essential skills for establishing meaningful connections, resolving conflicts, and collaborating effectively with others. By practicing social interactions in a controlled environment, students build confidence and improve their interpersonal competencies.

Activities that nurture critical thinking and decision-making abilities prepare students to face adult challenges more effectively. Engaging in these practices enhances their capacity to solve complex issues, make informed decisions, and adapt to changing environments. Students learn to analyze situations critically, weigh options, and implement solutions, which are crucial skills for personal and professional success.

Role-playing and considering various perspectives allow students to grow their capacity for empathy, a key component of positive interaction. This practice helps them understand and appreciate diverse viewpoints, fostering stronger and more meaningful connections. Enhanced empathy contributes to peaceful relationships and reduces the likelihood of disagreements by promoting understanding and compassion.

Mastering the art of communication is invaluable in every facet of life. Students who refine their communicative abilities through role-play and scenario-based discussions position themselves for greater achievements in both professional and personal contexts. Effective communication skills enable them to articulate ideas clearly, listen actively, and engage in constructive dialogue, which are essential for success in any field.

When it comes to peer teaching, students prepare a short lesson or presentation on a specific topic for their classmates. This requires them to thoroughly understand the material (indicating effective critical thinking), and then explain it in a clear and

engaging way (utilizing strong speaking skills). Peer teaching also involves responding to peers' questions, which further tests both their knowledge and their ability to communicate under pressure (Billings, L., & Roberts, T. 2006).

To practice the reflective oral journals, instead of writing, students keep an oral journal where they reflect on their learning experiences, discuss their progress in a certain subject, and set future learning goals. This activity encourages students to critically evaluate their own performance and articulate their thoughts and feelings about their learning journey. These activities not only enhance students' speaking abilities but also deepen their critical thinking skills by challenging them to analyze situations, evaluate different viewpoints, justify their thinking, and communicate their ideas and conclusions effectively. This dual development is crucial for academic success and essential for meaningful participation in society.

Conclusion

Critical thinking plays a vital role in language learning, enhancing students' ability to analyze, evaluate, and synthesize information. This process supports deeper comprehension of linguistic structures and cultural contexts, essential for effective communication. In the classroom, incorporating activities that promote critical thinking can significantly enhance students' learning experiences. Role-playing, scenario discussions, debates, Socratic seminars, and peer teaching are all effective methods for integrating critical thinking with language skills. These activities develop students' communicative abilities and foster creativity, empathy, and problem-solving skills. Mastering the art of communication is invaluable in every aspect of life. Students who refine their communicative abilities through role-play and scenario-based discussions position themselves for greater achievements in both professional and personal contexts. To maximize the benefits of critical thinking in language learning, educators should integrate engaging and visually appealing tasks which provide real-world contexts. Ultimately, critical thinking enriches language learning by encouraging students to analyze, evaluate, and synthesize information. It supports deeper comprehension of linguistic structures and cultural contexts, essential for effective communication. Promoting critical thinking in education not only enhances students' academic success but also prepares them for meaningful participation in society. By fostering critical thinking, educators equip students with the skills necessary to navigate complex social situations, solve problems, and communicate effectively, thereby contributing to their overall personal and professional development.

References:

1. Billings, L., & Roberts, T. (2006). Planning, practice, and assessment in the Socratic seminar. *The High School Journal*, 90(1), 1-12.

2. Brookfield, S. D. (1991). *Developing Critical Thinkers: Challenging Adults to Explore Alternative Ways of Thinking and Acting*. Jossey-Bass/Open University Press.
3. Brown, H. D. (2007). *Principles of Language Learning and Teaching*. Pearson Education. P.-47.
4. Cottrell, S. (2011). *Critical Thinking Skills: Developing Effective Analysis and Argument (Palgrave Study Skills) 2nd Edition*. P.-89.
5. Dewey, J. (1910). *How We Think*. D.C. Heath & Co.; Adler, M. J. (1982). *The Paideia Proposal: An Educational Manifesto*. Macmillan Publishing Company; Arnold, M., Hodgkinson, C., & Tilghman, B. (1988). *Human Action, Deliberation, and Causation*. University Press of America.
6. Halpern, D. F. (1996). *Thought and Knowledge: An Introduction to Critical Thinking*. Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
7. Halvorsen, A. (2005). Incorporating critical thinking skills development into ESL/EFL courses. *The Internet TESL Journal*, XI(3). Retrieved from <http://iteslj.org/Techniques/Halvorsen-CriticalThinking.html>
8. Kinoshita, C. Y. (2003). Integrating language learning strategy instruction into ESL/EFL lessons. *The Language Teacher*. Volume 7(5), 16-19.
9. Moon A. Jennifer. *Critical Thinking. An Exploration of Theory and Practice*. 2008. 248 Pages.
10. Mukhamedov A. (2023). Approaches to teaching critical thinking to English language learners. *Pedagog - Respublika Ilmiy Jurnali*. P.24-25.
11. Parker, W. C., & Hess, D. E. (2001). Teaching with and for discussion. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 17(3), 273-289.
12. Roberts, M., & Billings, A. (1999). Teaching critical thinking: Using seminars for 21st-century literacy. *Journal of Education for Teaching*, 25(3), 191-203.
13. TED. (n.d.). Ideas worth spreading. Retrieved from <https://www.ted.com>
14. Vasilopoulos, G. (2008). Adapting communicative language instruction in EFL contexts. *TESL Reporter*, 41(1), 30-39.